

Synthesis of Benzofuro[2,3-*c*]pyridinones, Naphtho[2',3' : 5,4]-furo[2,3-*c*]pyridin-1-ones and Naphtho[1',2' : 5,4]furo[2,3-*c*]pyridin-1-ones. Part-I

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The literature of benzofuropyridinones and naphthofuropyridinones is scanty but they can be looked upon as compounds having potential medicinal activity.

Usgaonkar *et al.*¹ studied reaction of DMF/POCl₃ on a number of compounds having structural features HOOC-CH=CH-CH₂COOH to prepare isoquinolones, β-carbolinones and pyranobenzofuro-pyridinones. We now extend the reaction to synthesise benzofuropyridinones and naphthofuro-pyridinones by action of DMF/POCl₃ on 2-carboxy-6-methylbenzofuran-3-acetic acid (3a), 2-carboxynaphtho[2,3-*b*]furan-3-acetic acid (3b) and 2-carboxynaphtho[1,2-*b*]furan-3-acetic acid (3c) (Scheme 1).

The acids (1a-c) were prepared² by condensing citric acid with *m*-cresol, β-naphthol and α-naphthol respectively, which on bromination gave the respective bromo derivatives (2a-c). Compounds 2a-c on heating with alcoholic potassium hydroxide yielded the required acids (3a-c). Compounds 3a-c on treatment with dimethyl formamide and phosphorous oxychloride at 0° gave 4-*N,N*-dimethylaminomethyl-1,3-dione derivatives (4a-c). The same reaction when carried out at 100° yielded 4-carboxy-2-methylfuro-pyridinone derivatives (5a-c). The diones (4a-c) on heating with POCl₃ at 100° furnished 5a-c respectively, showing that the diones are intermediates in the formation of 5a-c.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian A-60 spectrometer.

Compounds 1a-c: A mixture of citric acid (0.1 mol) and H₂SO₄ (32 ml) was stirred for 0.5 h at room temperature and then at 70°. *m*-Cresol, β naphthol or α-naphthol (for 1a, b, and c respectively) (0.1 mol) was added to it at 10° with stirring. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 h, then poured on crushed ice. The solid triaturated with aqueous NaHCO₃, filtered and acidified with concentrated HCl and crystallised from acetic acid: 1a, m.p. 199° (Found: C, 65.9; H, 4.50. C₁₂H₁₀O₄ requires: C, 66.00; H, 4.58%); ν_{max} 1735 (C=O of COOH) and 1712 cm⁻¹ (C=O); 1b, m.p. 209°; 1c, 190°.

Compounds 2a-c: Bromine acetic acid (16 ml; 10%) was added to 1a, b or c (0.013 mol) in acetic acid (60 ml) with stirring at room temperature for 3 h. The solid separated was crystallised from ethanol: 2c, m.p. 212° (Found: C, 54.10; H, 2.8. C₁₂H₉O₂Br requires: C, 54.00; H, 2.7%); ν_{max} 1760 (C=O of COOH) and 1715 cm⁻¹ (C=O); 2a, m.p. 184°; 2b, 182°.

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) Br₂/HAc, (ii) Alc. KOH, (iii) DMF/POCl₃, 0°, (iv) DMF/POCl₃, 100°, (v) POCl₃, 100°, (vi) Δ, above m.p., (vii) MeOH/H₂SO₄, 100°.

Compounds 3a–c : Compounds **2a, b** or **c** (0.003 mol) was refluxed with alcoholic KOH (10 ml ; 20%) for 4 h, then cooled, diluted and acidified with HCl. The solid formed was crystallised from ethyl acetate : **3b**, m.p. 258° (Found : C, 66.60 ; H, 3.60. $C_{15}H_{10}O_8$ requires : C, 66.66 ; H, 3.70%) ; **3a**, m.p. 224° ; **3c**, 185°.

Compounds 4a–c : $POCl_3$ (0.8 ml) was added to DMF (5 ml) and **3a, b** or **c** (0.0040 mol) at 0° with stirring. The mixture was stirred for 2 h, then poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid crystallised from benzene : **4a** (Found : C, 66.38 ; H, 4.7 ; N, 5.10. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N$ requires : C, 66.42 ; H, 4.79 ; N, 5.16%) ; ν_{max} 1 760–1 720 cm^{-1} (twin C=O of anhydride) ; **4b**, m.p. 254° ; **4c**, 148°.

Compounds 5a–c : The above stirred mixture was heated at 100° for 3 h, then poured on crushed ice and crystallised from acetic acid : **5a**, m.p. 246° (Found : C, 65.30 ; H, 4.20 ; N, 5.39. $C_{14}H_{11}O_4N$ requires : C, 65.36 ; H, 4.28 ; N, 5.44%) ; ν_{max} 1 760 (C=O of COOH) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O) ; δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.8 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 7.2–9 (4H, m, ArH) and 12.2 (1H, s, COOH), m/z M^+ 257 ; **5b**, m.p. 281° ; **5c**, 189°.

Decarboxylation of 5a–c to 6a–c : **5a–c** (0.2 g)

was heated above the m.p. The solid collected on the side of the tube was crystallised from benzene : **6a**, m.p. 120° (Found : C, 73.20 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 6.50. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N$ requires : C, 73.23 ; H, 5.16 ; N, 6.57%) ; **6b**, m.p. 105° ; **6c**, 115°.

Esterification of 5a–c to 7a–c : **5a–c** (0.5 g) was refluxed with methanol (50 ml) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (0.5 ml) for 16 h, then cooled and diluted. The solid was triaturated with aqueous $NaHCO_3$, filtered and crystallised from methanol : **7c**, m.p. 105° ; δ 2.8 (3H, s, $COOCH_3$), 3.8 (3H, s, N- CH_3), 4.6 (1H, s, allylic) and 7.3–8.85 (6H, m, ArH) ; **7a**, m.p. 156° ; **7b**, 115°.

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